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On graph theory and topologically frustrated polymers

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We prove the existence of graph-theoretic topological frustration in the quasi one-dimensional periodic bipartite lattice that is based on the two-dimensional honeycomb lattice.

1. Introduction

Topologically frustrated or concealed non-Kekuleans are very rare species constituting only about 0.1% of all planar hydrocarbons [1,2]. They were long hunted for their magnetic applications [3]. Some of these rare molecules have recently been produced with synthetic chemistry [4]. It is interesting to note that analogous structures could also exist when one moves from a planar to cylindrical topology or a periodic quasi-one-dimensional lattice as implied by recent covalent bonding of concealed non-Kekuleans [5].

2. Results and discussion

Let us formulate an *existence theorem*:

Theorem 2.1. *For a bipartite hexagonal graph G on a cylinder, an even number of vertices N , and equal number of vertices N_A and N_B in each of the two disjoint independent sets A and B are not sufficient conditions to ensure a zero deficit of the graph $\eta = N - 2\nu$, where ν is the cardinality of the maximum matching of the graph.*

Proof. Assume that $\eta = 0$ is always possible for any G . Let us now construct G as shown in Fig. 1(a,b). For any finite bipartite graph, Hopcroft–Karp algorithm [6] can be applied to find a maximum-cardinality matching. By running the algorithm on the obtained cylindrical graph, one gets $\eta = 2$, see Fig. 1(c).

Figure 1. Theorem 2.1 counter example. (a) The “double diamond ring” graph G with sets A and B colored as red and blue, respectively. It has $N = 54$ and $N_A = N_B = 27$. (b) An unrolled graph from panel (a) – “butterfly”. (c) Maximum cardinality matching (thick, light green) returned by Hopcroft-Karp algorithm. (d) Topologically frustrated polymer.

Corollary. Imposing a periodic boundary condition on a hexagonal bipartite graph with even N and $N_A = N_B$ does not guarantee $\eta = 0$.

As a result, one can infer that topological frustration is possible not only in planar hydrocarbons like Clar’s goblet, but also in cylindrical ones. Some regular cylindrical species have been synthesized as carbon nanobelts [7]. Likewise, a special class of one-dimensional materials that can be referred to as *topologically frustrated polymers/graphene nanoribbons* must exist, see Fig. 1(d). The metallic olympicene nanoribbon [8], which shares the same acene base with our counter example, used in proving Theorem 2.1, does not belong to this predicted class.

Finally, we note that the nullity theorem [9] does not apply to frustrated polymers. Despite $\eta = 2$, the “butterfly” graph spectrum features 4 zero eigenvalues.

3. Conclusion

It has been shown that concealed non-Kekuleans must exist within the class of hydrocarbons called carbon nanobelts and graphene nanoribbons/polymers. The abundance of such structures as well as their physical properties are both interesting yet open questions.

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References

1. Gutman I. 1974 Some topological properties of benzenoid systems. *Croat. Chem. Acta* **46**, 209–2015.
2. Cyvin SJ, Brunvoll J, Cyvin BN. 1990 The hunt for concealed non-Kekulean polyhexes. *J. Math. Chem.* **4**, 47–54. ([10.1007/BF01170003](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01170003))
3. Wang WL, Yazyev OV, Meng S, Kaxiras E. 2009 Topological frustration in graphene nanoflakes: Magnetic order and spin logic devices. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **102**, 157201. ([10.1103/PhysRevLett.102.157201](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.102.157201))

4. Mishra S, Beyer D, Eimre K, Kezilebieke S, Berger R, Gröning O, Pignedoli CA, Müllen K, Liljeroth P, Ruffieux P, Feng X, Fasel R. 2020 Topological frustration induces unconventional magnetism in a nanographene. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **15**, 22–28. ([10.1038/s41565-019-0577-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-019-0577-9))
5. Zhao C, Catarina G, Zhang JJ, Henriques JCG, Yang L, Ma J, Feng X, Gröning O, Ruffieux P, Fernández-Rossier J, Fasel R. 2024 Tunable topological phases in nanographene-based spin-1/2 alternating-exchange Heisenberg chains. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **19**, 1789–1795. ([10.1038/s41565-024-01805-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-024-01805-z))
6. Hopcroft JE, Karp RM. 1973 An $n^{5/2}$ algorithm for maximum matchings in bipartite graphs. *SIAM J. Comput.* **2**, 225–231. ([10.1137/0202019](https://doi.org/10.1137/0202019))
7. Cheung KY, Watanabe K, Segawa Y, Itami K. 2021 Synthesis of a zigzag carbon nanobelt. *Nat. Chem.* **13**, 255–259. ([10.1038/s41557-020-00627-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41557-020-00627-5))
8. McCurdy RD, Delgado A, Jiang J, Zhu J, Wen ECH, Blackwell RE, Veber GC, Wang S, Louie SG, Fischer FR. 2023 Engineering robust metallic zero-mode states in olympicene graphene nanoribbons. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **145**, 15162–15170. ([10.1021/jacs.3c01576](https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.3c01576))
9. Fajtlowicz S, John PE, Sachs H. 2005 On maximum matchings and eigenvalues of benzenoid graphs. *Croat. Chem. Acta* **78**, 195–201.